

The Impact of Human Resource Diversity and Organizational Integrity on Enhancing the Quality of Services Provided: A Field Study on Employees at Rafidain Bank in Baghdad

Hussam fahmi aajami

PhD in Business Administration, and an employee at the College of Electrical Engineering Technology

ARTICLE INFO

Published Online:
23 July 2025

Corresponding Author:
Hussam fahmi aajami

KEYWORDS: Human resource diversity, organizational integrity, service quality, customer satisfaction, Rafidain Bank, Baghdad.

ABSTRACT

This research aims to examine the impact of human resource diversity and organizational integrity on improving the quality of services provided at Rafidain Bank in Baghdad. Diverse human resources represent a key pillar of the contemporary work environment, contributing to enriching institutional performance through diverse experiences, cultures, and skills. Organizational integrity is a crucial factor in enhancing both internal and external trust, as well as ensuring transparency and accountability in the provision of banking services.

The research employed a descriptive-analytical approach, utilizing a questionnaire specifically designed for this purpose and distributed to a sample of employees at Rafidain Bank branches in Baghdad. The results revealed a statistically significant positive relationship between human resource diversity, organizational integrity, and improved service delivery. Institutions that adopt diversity and integrity policies achieve higher performance in terms of customer satisfaction and service quality.

The research recommends the need to inculcate values of integrity within the workplace and adopt effective mechanisms to manage diversity among employees, which will positively impact the quality of banking services provided.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's dynamic business environment, organizations are increasingly recognizing the critical role of workforce diversity and organizational integrity in enhancing service quality and customer satisfaction. The banking sector, in particular, relies heavily on the efficiency and reliability of its human capital to deliver high-quality services. Rafidain Bank, as one of the largest and oldest financial institutions in Iraq, faces growing pressure to improve its service delivery mechanisms to meet customer expectations and remain competitive. This study explores the impact of human resource diversity and organizational integrity on the quality of services provided by Rafidain Bank in Baghdad.

Despite ongoing reforms and modernization efforts, many public banks in Iraq, including Rafidain Bank, continue to encounter challenges related to service quality, customer satisfaction, and internal efficiency. A key concern is whether the diversity of human resources and the level of organizational integrity are effectively leveraged to enhance

service performance. Therefore, the core problem this research seeks to address is:

"To what extent do human resource diversity and organizational integrity contribute to improving the services provided by Rafidain Bank in Baghdad?"

This study is significant for several reasons. First, it provides empirical insights into the role of human capital diversity and ethical standards in improving public banking services in Iraq. Second, it contributes to the limited academic literature on organizational behavior and service performance in the Iraqi banking sector. Third, the findings can assist decision-makers in Rafidain Bank in formulating policies that promote inclusion, transparency, and excellence in service delivery, ultimately enhancing customer satisfaction and institutional trust.

The research aims to examine the level of human resource diversity at Rafidain Bank branches in Baghdad; assess the level of organizational integrity practiced in the bank's operations; analyze the relationship between workforce diversity and service improvement; evaluate the impact of

organizational integrity on service delivery; and propose recommendations for improving service quality through diversity and integrity strategies.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

1. human resource diversity

1.1. concept of human resource diversity.

Diversity refers to the variability of existence in terms of dissimilarity and difference of type. According to the Oxford Dictionary, the term "diversity" is used to describe different types of workers in organizations. It can be seen in the ways these workers communicate to themselves that others are different (Al-Obaidi, 2010: 31). When discussing Diversity, it refers to the characteristics of individuals that shape their identity and experiences in the workplace. Diversity also refers to the degree of differences among members of a group or organization (Al-Obaidi, 2010: 31). Diversity originates from biology, as it relates to the flourishing of species in nature. Diversity, in the social and behavioral sciences, refers to the differences between individuals and groups in terms of age, health, race, cultural background, gender, sexual orientation, religion, and ideology (Diez et al., 2011: 325). The globalization of business and the changing demographics of labor markets worldwide have generated significant interest in Diversity and diversity management among management scholars and practitioners. Organizational leaders must not only be aware of the Diversity of their human resources but also take action to address it. Being aware is not enough. They must also understand what Diversity is and how to foster and embrace it to achieve organizational goals. This Diversity in their human resources requires leaders to recognize and appreciate the differences among employees, as well as to understand that each person is unique and distinct. This places a significant burden on leaders and organizational management to identify the differences present in their workforce and to manage these differences effectively (Aigare et al., 2011).

Diversity management in organizations dates back to the 1960s in the United States, following the adoption of equal employment opportunity laws and affirmative action programs protecting minority workforces in American states. The concept has been used since the 1970s, initially to refer to minorities and women in the workforce. For a long time, it was common for managers to define workplace diversity as increasing gender equality, national and ethnic representation in the workforce. Based on the new constitutional amendments of 1974-1975, the US government strongly encouraged organizations to hire more women and minorities, providing them with greater opportunities to advance in the hierarchy (Jonsen et al., 2011; Abu Laifa, 2020, p. 268). Cultural diversity within the workplace has become increasingly important as more organizations adopt global workforce policies and link their impact to performance outcomes. With increasing globalization, interactions between

employees from diverse cultures, beliefs, backgrounds, and organizations are on the rise. Therefore, assessing and managing diversity is a key component of effective employee management, which in turn can improve workplace productivity (Mazur, 2010, p. 11). This has made diversity an issue that organizational leaders and employers must address wisely. Therefore, diversity indicators such as race, religion, gender, marital and family status, sexual orientation, and disability must be taken into account. Organizations can address diversity through several approaches: ignoring diversity, embracing diversity, fostering general acceptance of diversity, and creating an inclusive culture that values and promotes diversity. An organization's success in managing diversity requires the buy-in of all components of the organizational structure, from senior management to the lowest-ranking employees. The outcomes of diversity should also be studied, with management's responsibility for achieving these outcomes dependent on the returns it expects. Once management's responsibility for the consequences of diversity is established, a set of measures can be taken to manage diversity, including training on diversity acceptance (Saleh, 2021: 127). Diversity, in its broadest sense, extends beyond gender equality in the workplace, encompassing differences such as age, ethnic background, and educational level. It encompasses acceptance, respect, and an understanding that each individual is unique, and therefore, individual differences should be acknowledged. Differences also include socioeconomic status, age, physical abilities, religious and political beliefs, and other ideologies (Ahmed, 2017: 301). The primary objective of any organization, whether a service or production organization, is to achieve a competitive advantage and maximize its performance. For an organization to achieve its goals, it must effectively manage the diversity of its human resources. Diversity, in general, is the expression of differences and variations. However, researchers differed in their definitions of the concept of human resource diversity, and their viewpoints varied according to each researcher's perspective on diversity (Samara, 2017: 45).

Diversity is defined as "how the cultures, qualifications, and experiences of social groups and societies are expressed, and the diversity within them, and is a major source of creativity" (Carmer, 2011: 225).

In her study (Al-Obaidi, 2010: 32), Al-Obaidi defined diversity as "a term that denotes the differences existing among employees within a single organization in terms of age, gender, race, origin, religion, physical ability, color, or an individual's political, social, ideological, religious, or other orientations." Diversity has become a prevalent activity in human resource management and business organizations.

Diversity has gained greater attention today than in the past, due to increased global migration, the possibility of people connecting via the internet, and management's continued search for cheap resources (Marques, 2008: 5).

These and other reasons have led to the rise of diversity in the workplace. Managing diversity is a skill that leaders can learn in inclusive environments, as well as attitudes that can be accepted. The key to this is leaders' awareness that diversity is an essential advantage in the workplace, through the support provided by a multicultural workforce, which helps in understanding diverse customers. It also facilitates the organization's access to myriad markets through its human resources, which can renew and innovate, ensuring the loyalty of these highly skilled and talented employees (Al-Obaidi, 2010: 32-33). Ardakani et al. (2016: 408) also defined it as "the differences that comprise the individual, such as culture, race, nationality, age, religion, disability, gender, education, beliefs, and all differences in the workforce." In this context of defining diversity, Saleh (2021: 128) described it as "any clear difference between individuals: in age, race, religion, job specialization, profession, sexual orientation, geographic origin, lifestyle, institutional ownership, position, or any other clear difference."

Regarding the issue of diversity in organizations, it is necessary to point out that diversity management specializes in addressing issues related to the diversity of human resources and their relationship, on the other hand, to laws that stipulate the protection of specific groups or minorities (Saleem et al., 2011: 17). Sometimes, confusion occurs between diversity management and equality. Equality means treating all employees within an organization fairly and consistently, regardless of their background or position. In contrast, diversity management means accepting a diverse group of individuals to form the workforce and realize the potential of all, not for the benefit of any one group (Samara, 2017: 46). Bozhko (2014:11) also defined diversity management as "organizational work in itself, and this management was established to create a greater common culture among employees from many diverse backgrounds in formal and informal organizational structures."

The authors, including Brown et al. (2001), Daft & Nose (2002), Moussa (2007), and Brown (2008), differed from the previous group of authors by expanding the dimensions of diversity to include twenty-three dimensions, dividing them into three groups:

The first group: Internal dimensions of diversity, which includes several dimensions such as age, gender, sexual orientation, physical abilities, origin, and ethnicity.

The second group: External dimensions, which also include a set of sub-dimensions such as residence, income, personal habits, hobbies, religion or religious beliefs, educational background, scientific experience, physical appearance, parental status, and marital status.

The third and final group: Organizational dimensions of diversity, which includes a set of sub-dimensions such as job level, job content, work group, experience or seniority, union membership, and management's attitude toward diversity.

2. Organizational Integrity

2.1 Concept and Definition

The word integrity originates from the Latin term (*integritas*), meaning "perfection" or "completeness." It also refers to uprightness, purity, and moderation. The effectiveness of organizational integrity (OI) depends on the completeness of the rules of conduct in regulating the behavior of the individual employee. Two main concepts form the basis for employees' understanding of organizational integrity, defined by De Souza (2020: 37-40):

A. Adherence to rules: Organizational integrity refers to the organization's alignment with laws, codes of conduct, and public service procedures.

B. Applying work values: Organizational integrity refers to acting impartially, transparently, and honestly in the workplace, with rewards and punishments distributed equally regardless of the individual's position. Transparency refers to acting publicly by rules and regulations, while credibility refers to honesty in work relationships between individuals and in the provision of services. Organizational integrity is defined as an organizational behavior that is consistent with the values, standards, and norms accepted by service stakeholders. An organization's integrity is founded on its core values and expressed through formal codes of conduct. Boudrias et al. (2020: 5) argue that organizational integrity refers to the perception that organizational representatives adhere to and maintain ethically accepted values or practices that are perceived as being in use within the organization. This implies the recognition that positive employee behavior is treated fairly and respectfully, while the organization punishes unethical behavior. Magnier-Watanabe et al. (2020: 4) define organizational integrity as the organization's continuous operation in good faith, emphasizing honesty, trustworthiness, and honor within the organization. Organizational integrity is generally understood as organizational actions that are consistent with ethical or socially accepted values and respond effectively to its external environment.

From this perspective, Fiorito & Ehrenhard (2019:1-2) define organizational integrity as the interconnection between the ethical values formally adopted by senior management, the implicit values reflected in formal organizational systems and structures, shared by organizational members in daily organizational routines, beliefs, customs, and traditions, and the values enacted in organizational procedures. A study by Fuerst & Luetge (2021:5-6) demonstrated that the concept of integrity is linked to four dimensions of meaning: truthfulness, validity, integrity, and perfection. Integrity is often confused with righteousness, but in reality, integrity is a complex set of moral virtues that focus on the ethical aspects of organizational behavior. Organizational integrity is divided into two parts:

A. It can be seen in or through the decisions, and thus actions, of its members (individual actions).

B. It can be observed through the organization's actions (organizational actions).

The researcher provides an operational definition of organizational integrity as the extent to which health sector organizations adhere to ethical principles and standards, which are embodied in managerial practices and behaviors, and reflected in the perceptions and actions of working individuals

Boudrias et al. (2020: 3-4) found that organizational integrity contributes to the following:

a. It promotes positive employee behaviors, which ultimately benefit the organization's overall performance.

b. It is positively associated with employee creativity, organizational citizenship behaviors, and organizational identity, such as job satisfaction.

c. It contributes to maintaining a cohesive social system within the organization, which is crucial for the organization's survival

Zeng et al. (2020: 4) noted that leaders play a crucial role in shaping subordinates' attitudes and reducing their intentions to engage in unethical behavior toward the organization, its customers, and coworkers. This stems from Kohlberg's (1969) model, which suggested that individuals at the traditional level of moral reasoning should use the expectations of others (such as peers, family, or society at large) to determine what is ethical, allowing leaders within an organization to shape their perception of what is moral. A leader's integrity may be a situational factor that determines ethical or unethical behavior within an organization. As such, leaders may be able to encourage ethical behavior by modeling how to handle ethical issues within the organization. Leadership integrity reflects employees' perceptions of the alignment between leaders' words and actions in managing the organization. They are viewed as representatives of the organization, and their behavior will consequently influence employees' attitudes toward the organization. Employees who perceive leaders' behavior as being characterized by integrity and transparency are more engaged in their work. An honest leader will instill confidence in employees that the best thing to do is to connect deeply with the work and the required roles. Organizational integrity is also referred to as the alignment between words and actions. Some studies on perceived integrity have focused only on "authenticity," while others have focused on perceived behavioral integrity, "the alignment between words and actions." Recent studies have observed a shift toward integrity as the actual behavior of leaders and managers, particularly in terms of examining performance and business outcomes (Al-Abrow et al., 2018: 3) and (Nangoli et al., 2020: 3).

3. Service Quality

3.1 Concept of Service Quality

It is challenging for any business or organization to overlook quality. Organizations build a reputation through the quality of their products and services, which enables them to achieve high profits and save costs that would otherwise be incurred if their products and services were of poor quality.

This is why all organizations are paying attention to quality, as they realize that high-quality products and services can be a significant competitive advantage for an organization. Quality management has evolved beyond simply avoiding errors; it has become an approach to managing and enhancing the organization's overall operations (Slack & Brandon-Jones, 2018, p. 459).

Schroeder & Goldstein (2018: 139) defined quality as "meeting or exceeding customer requirements now and in the future." Al-Zaidi and Al-Azzi (2021: 175) emphasized that quality is "a dynamic state associated with products, services, people, processes, and environments that meet or exceed expectations and help produce superior value. In other words, quality is a constantly changing state, meaning that what is considered quality today may not be good enough to be considered quality tomorrow." Bozarth & Handfield (2019:110) defined quality as "a product or service free of deficiencies." Aziz (2020:163) viewed quality as "a measure of the degree to which the actual performance of the service provided by an organization matches customer expectations, or the difference between customer expectations of the service and their perception of it. It reflects the customer's assessment of the organization's superiority in service delivery. Based on the above, the researcher believes that the term "service quality" can be applied to banking services that meet or exceed customer needs and desires with higher specifications. This is achieved by involving the customer from the outset in the banking service design process to produce services that meet their needs and wishes.

Service quality assessments are conducted during the service delivery process. Customer satisfaction with a service can be determined by comparing expectations about the service with the actual service provided. When expectations about the service match the service provided, the customer is satisfied. If expectations are exceeded, the service is perceived as of exceptional quality, and the customer is satisfied and happy. When the service provided falls below expectations, the quality of the service is considered unacceptable, and the customer is dissatisfied. These expectations are based on several sources, including word of mouth, personal needs, and previous experience (Bordoloi et al., 2019: 150). There is a set of dimensions to measure service quality, including (Schroeder & Goldstein, 2018: 142):

1. Tangibles (aesthetics): The appearance of physical facilities, equipment, furniture, and personnel clothing in a service organization. The more attention the organization pays to these aspects, the higher the perceived quality.

2. Reliability: This refers to the service organization's ability to perform the service on time, accurately, and without errors.

3. Responsiveness (support): This refers to the service organization's ability to provide prompt service to customers. The faster the service, the higher the perceived quality, and vice versa.

“The Impact of Human Resource Diversity and Organizational Integrity on Enhancing the Quality of Services Provided: A Field Study on Employees at Rafidain Bank in Baghdad”

4. Confidence and Empathy: This refers to the knowledge and courtesy demonstrated by service providers, as well as their ability to make customers feel reassured. It also encompasses the individual attention and care provided by the service organization to its customers.

III- RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a descriptive and analytical approach, aiming to explore the relationships among the main variables: human resource diversity, organizational integrity, and service improvement.

1. Research Hypotheses:

Based on the research problem and objectives, the study proposes the following hypotheses:

H1: There is a statistically significant relationship between human resource diversity and the improvement of services provided by Rafidain Bank in Baghdad.

H2: There is a statistically significant relationship between organizational integrity and the improvement of services provided by Rafidain Bank in Baghdad.

H3: The joint impact of human resource diversity and organizational integrity is significant in enhancing the quality of services at Rafidain Bank.

2 Data Collection Tool: A structured questionnaire was developed and validated to gather primary data. The questionnaire included Likert-scale items measuring perceptions of diversity, integrity, and service quality.

3.Data Analysis Techniques: Statistical tools such as SPSS were used to perform reliability tests, correlation analysis, and structural equation modeling (SEM) to test the hypotheses and evaluate the strength and significance of relationships between the variables.

4.Study Design: A cross-sectional design was employed to collect data at a single point in time, enabling a snapshot analysis of the current organizational context.

5.Population and Sample: The study targets employees working in various branches of Rafidain Bank in Baghdad. A purposive sample of (390) individuals was selected based on their suitability to the study topic, with a number of respondents representing service provision and management positions.

IV- RESULTS

1. Description of the study sample characteristics: Regarding the demographic variables (gender, age, educational level, number of years of dealing with the bank), they can be explained in the following table:

Table 1: Characteristics of the study sample

Variable s	Distribution of variables	percentage	numbe r
gender	Male	%83.33	325
	Female	%16.66	65
Total		%100	390
Age	30 years and younger	%28.71	112
	31-40 years	%41.53	162
	41-50 years	%20.76	81
	51 years and older	%8.97	35
Total		%100	390
Educatio nal level	Preparatory school and below	%8.71	34
	Diploma	%8.71	34
	Bachelor's degree	%60.51	236
	Higher education certificate	%22.05	86
Total		%100	390
Number of years dealing with the bank	5 years and younger	%28.46	111
	6-15 years	%36.92	144
	16-20 years	%22.05	86
	20 years and older	%12.56	49
Total	Total	%100	390

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the SPSS 26 program.

From Table 1, we conclude the following:

1. Gender: The percentage of males is greater than that of females among the customers of the bank under study, as the number of males reached (325), representing (83.33%), while the number of females reached (65), representing (16.66%). This is normal and is due to the demographic nature of the society in which the bank operates, in which males dominate all exchange and trade professions.
2. Age: The highest percentage reached (41.53%) for the age group (31-40), followed by the age group (30 years and younger), which came to 28.71%. The age group (41-50) reached 20.76%, and the age group (51 years and older) came in last place with 8.97%. The results indicate that the majority of the bank's customers are within the 31-40 age group.
3. Educational level: The results indicate that most of the study sample members hold a bachelor's degree (60.51%), followed by those with postgraduate degrees (22.05%). In comparison, those with a diploma or preparatory school certificate or less each accounted for 8.71%. The results

“The Impact of Human Resource Diversity and Organizational Integrity on Enhancing the Quality of Services Provided: A Field Study on Employees at Rafidain Bank in Baghdad”

indicate that the study sample possessed sufficient knowledge to answer the questionnaire content.

4. Number of years of dealing with the bank: The results showed that the majority of the study sample had been dealing with the bank for 6-15 years, accounting for 36.92%. This was followed by those who had dealt with the bank for (5 years or less), accounting for (28.46%). Customers who had dealt with the bank for 16-20 years accounted for 22.05%, while those who had dealt with the bank for 20 years or more came in last place, accounting for 12.56%. Overall, this diversity in the number of years.

2. Testing the validity and reliability of the scale:

The researcher conducted a Cronbach's alpha coefficient test to measure the reliability of the questionnaire items. To be considered reliable, the scale must reach (0.70 alpha) according to (Bolarinwa, 2015:198). Table 2 shows the results of the reliability coefficient values for the main variables and the questionnaire as a whole:

Table 2: Results of the reliability test of the scale tool

Variables	Dimensions	Cronbach's alpha	correlation	Sig	Number of paragraphs
Diversity of human resources	Age	.950	.928	.000	5
	Origin	.958	.943	.000	5
	Race	.941	.977	.000	5
	Gender	.949	.981	.000	5
	Physical Abilities	.950	.985	.000	5
Diversity of human resources as a whole		.989	.968	.000	25
Organizational integrity	Honesty	.979	.795	.000	5
	Reform	.953	.994	.000	5
	Integration	.940	.994	.000	5
Organizational integrity as a whole		.984	.927	.000	
service quality	Tangible things	.981	.923	.000	5
	Responsiveness	.982	.925	.000	5
	and self-confidence	.986	.864	.000	5
Overall service quality		.993	.904	.000	15
As a whole, the survey		.995	.933	.000	55

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the SPSS 26 program.

It is clear from Table (2) that the stability values of the variables have exceeded the assumed value to indicate the stability of the tool, which is (70 Alpha≤0.) The questionnaire as a whole achieved a stability value of (0.995), which indicates that it is a very high statistical indicator. This means

that the study tool enjoys high stability, which gave the researcher the right to adopt its results and generalize them to the study community.

It is noted from the table above that all Pearson coefficient values for all dimensions were greater than 0.60, which indicates the existence of a strong relationship between the dimensions and the variables to which they belong. Accordingly, this means that all sub-dimensions are internally consistent with the main variables to which they belong.

3. Description and Diagnosis of Study Variables

Table (3) shows the arithmetic mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation for the study variables, as measured by the responses of the study sample members to the questionnaire items, in order to determine which variables are more important than others.

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance
Diversity of human resources	390	3.676	0.971	26.414
Organizational integrity	390	3.189	1.051	32.957
service quality	390	3.379	0.959	28.381

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the SPSS 26 program.

The results in the table above showed that the variable (diversity of human resources) achieved a coefficient of variation of 26.414, which is the lowest coefficient of variation; the variable (organizational integrity) achieved a coefficient of variation of 32.957, which is the highest coefficient of variation. The variable (quality of services) achieved a coefficient of variation of 28.381, which is the second lowest coefficient of variation among the variables. This indicates the accuracy of the answers and the limited dispersion, in addition to the study sample's conviction of the importance of the service capacity and the bank's absorptive capacity, which is considered one of the most important features that distinguishes the bank under study from competing banks. This is reinforced by the arithmetic mean of these variables, as the arithmetic mean of the human resources diversity variable reached 3.676, which is greater than the hypothetical mean of 3. This variable achieved a standard deviation of 0.971, indicating consistency in the study sample's responses to this variable. The variable of quality of banking services ranked second, with an arithmetic mean of 3.379 and a standard deviation of 0.959. The variable of organizational integrity ranked last, with an arithmetic mean of 3.189 and a standard deviation of 1.051.

4. Correlation test between variables

The researcher conducted a Pearson correlation coefficient test between the three variables to study the relationship between them.

Table 4: shows the test results

Correlations			
	Diversity of human resources	Organizational integrity	service quality
Diversity of human resources	1		
Organizational integrity	.945**	1	
service quality	.886**	.835**	1
** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the SPSS 26 program

Table 4 shows the results of the correlation test between the study variables. It was found that the diversity of human resources is positively related to the organizational integrity of the bank under study. The value of the correlation coefficient between them reached 0.945 at a significance level of 0.00, which is less than the conventional significance level of 0.05, indicating that the correlation between the two variables is statistically significant. The value of the correlation between the two variables indicates a strong direct correlation between them. This means that the diversity of human resources in the bank under study has a strong correlation with the bank’s organizational integrity.

The table above also indicates that human resource diversity and organizational integrity are positively correlated with improved service quality at the bank under study. The correlation coefficient between them reached 0.886 and 0.835 at a significance level of 0.00, which is lower than the conventional significance level of 0.05, indicating that the relationship between the variables is statistically significant. The correlation value between the three variables indicates a strong direct relationship between them. This means that human resource diversity and organizational integrity at the bank under study are closely related to the bank's service quality.

5. Testing the Impact Hypothesis

To test this hypothesis, structural equation modeling was used to measure the effect of the independent variable (human resource diversity) on the dependent variable (service quality). With the mediating variable (organizational integrity), Table (5) shows the results of the impact test.

Table 5: Results of testing the effect of service process decisions on organizational reputation

	R2	β	T	sig	F	sig	VIF
X → Z	.793	.968	43.249	.000	1870.5	.000	1.000
X → Y	.698	.927	22.689	.000	514.8	.000	1.000
Z → Y	.784	.939	28.469	.000	818.5	.000	1.000
X → Z → Y		.940			403.5	.000	

Source: Prepared by the researcher based on the SPSS 26 program

The results of the impact test on human resource diversity, organizational integrity, and service quality are presented in Table 5 above. The results show that the value of (F) reached (1870.5), (818.5), and (514.8), respectively, at a significant level of (0.00), which is less than the considerable level of (0.05). This result confirms the significance of the effect between the variables, indicating that human resource diversity has a significant impact on organizational integrity, as evidenced by the coefficient of determination (R2) value of 0.79. This result suggests that human resource diversity accounts for 79% of the variance in the organizational integrity variable at the bank under study. As for the remaining percentage (21%), it is due to other factors not included in the study model. The study also demonstrated the impact of the variables of human resource diversity and organizational integrity on the dependent variable of service quality, with a coefficient of determination (R2) of 0.78. This result indicates that human resource diversity explains 78% of the variance in the service quality variable. In the bank under study, the remaining 22% is attributed to factors not included in the study model. The value of the coefficient of determination (R2) reached 0.69. This result indicates that organizational integrity accounts for 69% of the variance in the service quality variable at the bank under study. The remaining percentage (31%) is due to other factors not included in the study model. In contrast, the regression coefficient (β) reached a value of (0.96) (0.92) (0.93) respectively, which is a significant effect according to the calculated (T) value of (43.249) (43.249) 28.469) at a significance level of (0.00), which is less than the significance level of (0.05). This means that a one-unit change in the diversity variable in human resources leads to an increase in both organizational integrity and service quality. Therefore, this result confirms the validity of the hypotheses, which state that there is a direct significant effect relationship between diversity in human resources and integrity in improving the quality of services in the bank.

“The Impact of Human Resource Diversity and Organizational Integrity on Enhancing the Quality of Services Provided: A Field Study on Employees at Rafidain Bank in Baghdad”

The figure above illustrates the direct and indirect, as well as total and partial, effects between the variables. This result suggests that human resource diversity, supported by sound management, fosters a climate of integrity and trust within the organization. Organizational integrity also enhances positive employee behavior and motivates them to improve the quality of banking services. It can be argued that the actual impact of resource diversity appears indirectly through the positive change it brings about in the internal work environment (integrity), leading to more effective and high-quality banking services at Rafidain Bank.

This model represents a significant application of organizational justice theory and human capital theory, where the elements of diversity and integrity complement each other to achieve the ultimate goal of enhancing service quality. The results indicate the need for banks—such as Rafidain Bank—to intelligently and professionally manage their human diversity, promoting integrity as a core value and ultimately leading to enhanced competitiveness through improved service quality.

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that both human resource diversity and organizational integrity play an essential role in enhancing the quality of services provided at Rafidain Bank. The analysis results showed that diversity in employee cultural, educational, and professional backgrounds contributes to improved innovation and expanded responsiveness to diverse customer needs. It also revealed that organizational integrity, as an ethical and behavioral framework governing employee performance, plays a pivotal mediating role in transforming this diversity into effective performance. The study suggests that a work environment characterized by transparency and fairness enhances an organization's capacity to deliver high-quality services.

RESULTS

1. There is a direct, positive relationship between human resource diversity and service quality, as diverse backgrounds contribute to enriching job performance and achieving customer satisfaction.
2. Organizational integrity plays a mediating role in influencing the relationship between diversity and service quality, meaning that the impact of diversity is most effective when coupled with honest and fair organizational behavior.

3. Employees at Rafidain Bank demonstrated an awareness of the importance of diversity and integrity; however, the practical application of these principles requires fostering a supportive corporate culture that promotes these values.

4. Data indicated that departments that practice the principles of fairness and transparency were better able to transform diversity into tangible added value in service quality.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Enhance training and awareness programs on the benefits of diversity and integrity within the workplace, increasing employee and departmental awareness of their importance in enhancing performance.
2. Adopt clear institutional policies that support functional and cultural diversity and prevent discrimination, ensuring a fair environment for all employees.
3. Activate ethical oversight mechanisms to ensure integrity in daily administrative and functional decisions, particularly those related to service delivery.
4. Link incentives and evaluations to employee performance in the areas of integrity and service quality, enhancing their commitment to institutional values.
5. Leverage successful international experiences in managing organizational diversity and integrity to develop an internal model appropriate for the Iraqi work environment.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmed, Azzam Abdel Nabi. (2017). A comparative study of diversity management mechanisms in pre-university education in Canada and Australia and the possibility of benefiting from them in Egypt, *Journal of Educational Administration*, Issue (16), December.
2. AL-Abrow, H., Abdullah, H., & Atshan, N. (2018). “Effect of organisational integrity and leadership behaviour on organisational excellence: Mediator role of work engagement”. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, Vol.27 No (4), pp.972-985.
3. Al-Obaidi, Nour Khalil. (2010). Building a high-inclusion management model within the framework of human resource diversity treatments and social capital development capabilities: A field study in the Iraqi Rashid Bank. Unpublished master's thesis. College of Administration and Economics, University of Baghdad.
4. Al-Zaidi, Nazem Jawad Abdul, Al-Azzi, Safa Adnan Mahmoud, (2021), “The Impact of Emotional Intelligence on the Organization’s Reputation: A Field Study of a Sample of Private Banks in Baghdad,” *Al-Riyada Journal of Finance and Business*, Volume 2, Issue 3.
5. Aziz, Adel Abdullah, (2020), “The Role of Business Intelligence Technologies in Improving the Organization’s Reputation: A Survey Study in the Private Telecommunications Sector/Nineveh

“The Impact of Human Resource Diversity and Organizational Integrity on Enhancing the Quality of Services Provided: A Field Study on Employees at Rafidain Bank in Baghdad”

- Governorate as a Model”, *Anbar University Journal of Economic and Administrative Sciences*, Volume 12, Issue 29.
6. Bordoloi, S., Fitzsimmons, J.A. & Fitzsimmons, M.J., (2019), "Service Management -Operations, Strategy, Information Technology-", Ninth Edition, Published by McGraw-Hill Education, New York.
 7. Boudrias, J. S., Rousseau, V., & Lajoie, D. (2021). "How lack of integrity and tyrannical leadership of managers influence employee improvement-oriented behaviors". *Journal of Business Ethics*, Vol.172 No (3), pp.487-502.
 8. Bozarth ,C.C.& Handfield,R.B.,(2019), " Operations management and supply chain", Fifth Edition, published by Pearson Education Limited, New York.
 9. De Souza, M. N. M. (2020). "Organizational Integrity and Corruption Decision-Making in The Ghanaian Public Service" (Doctoral dissertation, University of Ghana), pp.1-161.
 10. Fiorito, T., & Ehrenhard, M. (2019). "Understanding organizational integrity from an institutional perspective". In *Academy of Management Proceedings*, United States, Vol. 2019, No (1), p. 1-6.
 11. Fuerst, M. J., & Luetge, C. (2021). "The conception of organizational integrity: A derivation from the individual level using a virtue-based approach". *Business Ethics, the Environment & Responsibility*. 00, pp.1–9
 12. Magnier-Watanabe, R., Uchida, T., Orsini, P., & Benton, C. F. (2020). "Organizational virtuousness, subjective well-being, and job performance: Comparing employees in France and Japan". *Asia-Pacific journal of business administration*. Vol. 12 No (2), pp. 115-138
 13. Marques, J. (2008). Feature articles workplace diversity: Developing a win-win- win strategy. *Development and Learning in Organizations*, 22 (5). U.S.A.
 14. Nangoli, S., Muhumuza, B., Tweyongyere, M., Nkurunziza, G., Namono, R., Ngoma, M., & Nalweyiso, G. (2020). "Perceived leadership integrity and organisational commitment". *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 39 No (6), pp. 823-834
 15. Saleh, Rasha. (2021). *The Impact of Diversity and Inclusion Management on High-Performance Work Systems: A Field Study at Maysan Oil Company*. *Arab Journal of Management*, Volume (39), Issue (3), University of Basra.
 16. Samara, Nisreen Shaker Radwan. (2017). *The Reality of Diversity and Its Impact on Organizational Culture in Palestinian Universities - Gaza Governorates*. Unpublished Master's Thesis, Faculty of Commerce, Islamic University, Gaza, Palestine.
 17. Schroeder, R. & Goldstein, S.M., (2018), " Operations Management in the Supply Chain -Decisions and Cases-", Seventh Edition, Published by McGraw-Hill Education, New York.
 18. Slack,N. & Brandon-Jones,A. ,(2018)," Operations and Operations Management -Principles and Practices of Strategic Influence-",Fifth Edition, published by Pearson Education Limited, United Kingdom.
 19. Zeng, C., Kelly, S., & Goke, R. (2020). "Exploring the impacts of leader integrity and ethics on upward dissent and whistleblowing intentions". *Communication Reports*, Vol.33 No (2), pp.82-94.